

IMPROVEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF NATIONAL VALUES MECHANISMS THROUGH SPIRITUAL AND LEGAL EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS OF SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the reforms carried out in the field of education in Uzbekistan are devoted to the issues of improving the mechanisms of spiritual and legal education of students in the process of socialization, the development of scientific and pedagogical mechanisms of effective organization based on cultural-historical traditions, customs and universal values in the spiritual and legal education of young people. The current issue aimed at ensuring the priority of humanization of the educational process and necessary for the society was analyzed.*

Keywords: *socialization, spiritual and legal education, cultural and historical traditions, customs, universal values, family, community and neighborhood cooperation, youth loyalty to the motherland, entrepreneurship, will, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, improvement of mechanisms of innovative thinking, hard work, humanitarianism.*

Newly developing Uzbekistan pays special attention to the moral and legal education of young people on a global scale, and aims to inculcate in them the qualities that are compatible with our national values and traditions. In this regard, the development of mass media is causing the emergence of anti-social behavior, harmful ideas and ideological attacks that are contrary to our way of life, which endanger the life and health of young people. Along with necessary information, students who use foreign TV programs, radio broadcasts, Internet resources, mobile communication, computer games, video and film products are also faced with the propaganda of cruelty, violence, and other ideas alien to our national mentality, which are contrary to the moral rules of our society. . As a result, the need to form an information culture among students and raise their morale is becoming more and more urgent. To improve the technologies and innovative methods of using media to develop students as individuals and increase their social activity, to improve the diagnostic system of forming the spirituality of students based on mass media, to protect students from various ideological influences in the global information space and to ensure information security special attention is being paid to the improvement of mechanisms. In our country, large-scale work is being carried out in the direction of education and personal development of the young generation. In this regard, effective organizational, pedagogical forms and tools based on the rich national cultural-historical traditions, customs and universal values of our people were put into practice in the spiritual-ethical-legal education of the young generation. Improving the spiritual and legal education of students, increasing the social activity of young people, and raising them to be loyal and dedicated people to the Motherland has been studied as an actual pedagogical process that requires unity and continuity. In this regard, the Decree "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" occupies an important place. Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-406 "On State Policy Regarding Youth" dated September 14, 2016, No. O'RQ-444 "On Protection of Children from Information

Harmful to Their Health" dated September 8, 2017, "Spiritual-Educational Law" dated July 28, 2017 Resolution No. PQ-3160, dated January 12, 2017, "on improving the efficiency of work and raising the development of the industry to a new level" "Improving the system of printing and distribution of book products, book reading, it is appropriate to implement the tasks defined in other regulatory legal documents.

In the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyov, "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people", "We will continue our path of national development to a new level, while creating all the opportunities for the young generation entering the society", the theme of youth formation, their spiritual and legal education served as a basis for the researcher. Eastern thinkers Al-Bukhari, al-Hakim al-Tirmizi, Ibn Sina, Al-Biruni, Al-Farabi, Amir Temir, Alisher Navai, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Babur, Mirza Bedil, Ahmad Donish and Abdulla Avloni also paid a lot of attention in their works. Among the scientists of our republic, O. Jamolidinova, O. Musurmonova, A. Mirzaev, R. Safarova, H. Yu. Salomova, Sh. Olimov, , Kh.J. Khudoykulov, M.K. Hoshimova, M. In the creative works of K. Kuronov, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Makhmudov and N.M. Egamberdieva, special attention was paid to the issues of public cooperation in spiritual and legal education, methods of organizing educational processes for forming concepts of legal education among young people.

Today, the topic "Improving pedagogical-psychological features of national value mechanisms by providing moral and legal education of students in the process of socialization" has not yet been fully analyzed, taking into account local conditions, and in this regard, the topic has not been studied enough, and the relevance in this regard is of particular importance. In this regard, the positive moral and legal issues that are being carried out at the level of state policy have been specifically addressed. In the new third renaissance period of our great Uzbekistan, which is currently changing, the changes and achievements in the social, political and economic spheres of the state policy and the development of new production, the conditions created for the well-being of our people, the attention of the world community to develop their abilities and talents was recognized by, improving the technologies of moral and legal education in the process of socialization of students leads to scientific-based changes, looking for new areas and directions of today.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is independent from the day of achieving the status, even in the present New Uzbekistan period, the state and society set clear, concrete goals, which led to the development of the social activity of students and youth. Therefore, in the process of socialization of students in all spheres, social protection of moral and legal education, support of them as individuals and in their professional formation is in the attention of the state of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Declaring 2023 as the year of "Respecting the human being and quality education". In it, honoring young people by providing moral and legal education, directing them to science and enlightenment, preparing competitive personnel, at the same time, improving the technologies of providing moral and legal education in the process of socialization of students will be important, and the study of this topic is also a requirement of the time and era. . New scientific changes in the field of science, new legal research on spiritual and legal independence are being carried out in Uzbekistan through the process of education. Legal education does not mean giving influence on the legal slogans existing in a person's mind and thinking, character, in order to form life experience. Law is the standard of free will determined by law. Morality imposes human obligations on man. Morality is optional, law is mandatory.

The main goal of legal education is the formation of culture in students and the ability to live in a legal democratic state. Forms of spiritual and legal education are methods of external actions of spiritual and legal education. Moral and legal education can be implemented in different forms. For example, through education, propaganda. Moral and legal education gives practical help to young people in managing their actions in family, social relations and in their lives. Behavior is one of the concepts of ethics. It is a moral phenomenon related to the character of a person, and his actions within the framework of morality include decency and morality in addition to behavior. Morality manifests itself in socialized concepts and principles such as goodness and evil, justice, humanity, selflessness, behavior is reflected in concepts such as good and evil, duty, bravery, hospitality, and etiquette is expressed in modesty, honesty, modesty, honesty, truthfulness and other moral standards. . Today, the scientific-theoretical and moral-legal basis of improving cooperation in the formation of mechanisms of national values by providing moral-legal education of students in the process of socialization is important. In the legacy of Eastern thinkers, one of the problems of formation of mechanisms of national values by providing spiritual and legal education in the process of socialization of students. Pure pedagogical works were created in the period of the Eastern Renaissance, and educational scientists who left a name with their immortal teaching about the special and general methods of human development in education appeared on the field.

In particular, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi made an important contribution to the theory of knowledge. Abu Nasr Farabi emphasizes that a person cannot reach maturity alone, and says that he needs contact, support and relationships with others. Alisher Navoi pays attention to the role of science in human development and the importance of intelligence and perception formed on the basis of reading and learning in human life, as well as intellectual education and its essence. According to Abdulla Awlani, it is necessary to educate the body in order to have a healthy mind, good morals, and knowledge. Uzbek national pedagogue Abdulla Avloni defines ethics as follows: "Ethics is a science that calls people to goodness and prevents them from evil. A book that explains the goodness of good behavior and the badness of bad behavior with proofs is called ethics. Morality - teaches the norms of self-management in human life, the culture of dealing with others, the criteria of working honestly and living the right life. Ibn Sina expressed its meaning by saying: "Morality is the science of self-control for everyone." The norms and rules of ethics were formed and improved during the historical development and arose from people's living conditions, natural needs, social interests and vital requirements, and they were manifested in the behavior, behavior and relationships of people in a certain historical period.

Therefore, the acquisition of knowledge by students is an important issue. Reading information that students should master in the process of rapid reading includes facts, events, processes, laws, and methods of action. At the same time, deviations from the norms, non-compliance with the norms and actions against the law are often seen in students. Such deviations from the average norm, both positive and negative, have threatened the stability of society.

They include the following in the main forms of deviant behavior in a broader sense: 1. Drunkenness and alcoholism; 2. Drug addiction; 3. Crime alienation; 4. Suicide; 5. Prostitution; 6. Gambling and drug addiction.

The scientific study of such deviations is carried out in the field of crime research, socialization, social work, and pedagogy. Deviant behavior (lat. *Deviatio* — deviation, departure) means the following:

1. Behavior of a person that does not correspond to the "norms of mental health, law, culture or morality" created or officially established in society.

2. A social phenomenon that occurs in society or does not correspond to officially established norms (standards, models) and is reflected in public forms of human activity. Deviation in behavior is natural and necessary, since social changes are carried out through deviant behavior and the functioning of social systems is related to human life activities. They serve to increase the individual experience. The differences in the social-cultural, spiritual-ethical-legal status of people that arise on this basis are the conditions for the improvement of society and the realization of social development.

The norm in medicine is a completely healthy person, in pedagogy - a student who studies well in all subjects, and the absence of crimes in social life. The most difficult thing is to define a norm as a set of characteristics and a pattern of behavior common to most people.

In the process of socialization of students, moral and legal education was sufficiently evaluated through the development of knowledge and positive qualities to improve the technologies of education. In the process of socialization of students, the model of improving the technologies of moral and legal education is of particular importance.

Target component: It is evaluated by improving moral and legal education in the process of socialization of students. Improving students' adaptation to life and spiritual and legal knowledge. Study of the current situation, Use in practice, Study of the situation of making a plan of educational activities, Identification of technologies, Development of motives, Development of educational activities,

Tasks component: Methodological condition; Forms: Problem lectures; Problem seminars; Thematic methods: Brainstorming; "Round table"; "Cluster"; "Keys stadium"; Analysis of specific situations. Tools: Law and decrees; Codes; Scientific pedagogical literature; Survey; Formed criteria: rules of etiquette; knowledge of law; Extracurricular activities: Conference, club; moral and legal educational events; Meetings with experts and social networks.

Result evaluation component. Criteria: evaluation of motivational, emotional-cognitive, moral-legal behavior, legal consciousness. Levels: high, middle, low. In the process of socialization of students, it is assumed that the student has sufficient information, can understand their essence, and can interpret the content of certain concepts. In the process of socialization of students, the level of acquiring theoretical knowledge of moral and legal laws along with national, universal and socially significant values should be reflected in personal relationships. In the process of socialization of students, the decision of legal consciousness is made through the development of appropriate spiritual and legal education for citizens. In the process of socialization of students, a model of improving the technologies of moral and legal education suitable for citizens was developed. In the component of the final results, the socialization process of students was sufficiently evaluated by developing knowledge and positive qualities to improve moral and legal education suitable for citizens.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the process of socialization of students, the scientific and research work carried out on the technology of moral and legal education allowed to recommend the following from the results of observation and generalization:

1. In the process of socialization of students, spiritual and legal qualifications and skills were improved in their minds by providing spiritual and legal education.

2. In the process of socialization of students, attention was paid to the system of using

pedagogical technologies in spiritual and legal education, interdisciplinary connection and dependence in spiritual and legal education.

3. In the process of socialization of students, the need to use the huge spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, national values, customs and traditions accumulated over the centuries in the educational process was developed.

4. In the process of socialization of students, it was determined to determine the measures of learning and dissemination of best practices in the effective organization of spiritual and legal education suitable for citizens.

5. In the process of socialization of students, moral and legal education suitable for citizens was systematically launched.

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